

Innovative concepts and technologies for ECologically sustainable NUTRient management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

Newsletter – Issue 5

November 2025

WELCOME

Welcome to the fifth edition of the **Econutri** Newsletter! Within these pages, you will find news and updates on our activities. We invite you to subscribe and explore our website! Follow us on social media and learn more about the world of **Econutri**.

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Celebrating the third year of ECONUTRI

**4th General Assembly in Braga, Portugal
7-10 October 2025**

The **Econutri** consortium gathered in Braga, Portugal for a three-day General Assembly to celebrate the project's third year. It was hosted by [UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO](#) (UTAD). With 55 in-person participants, the meeting featured major scientific progress updates, including nutrient recycling, optimized fertilization, nature-based solutions, and socio-economic assessments. Stakeholders from Portugal and China shared their interest in **Econutri's** outcomes while a [field visit](#) to UTAD's demonstration site in Barcelos, showcased practical nutrient-smart innovations. The event strengthened teamwork and set the course for the project's final steps toward completion in April 2026.

A big thank you to **UTAD** for their warm hospitality, the lovely dinner and the wonderful walk around the historic center of Braga.

📖 Read the full article on our [website](#).

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During the **Econutri** General Assembly in Braga, the external advisors joined the meeting. Clive Rahn, one of the advisors from the University of Warwick, celebrated together with the partners 16 years of scientific collaboration between Warwick and the China Agricultural University (Dr. Chen) – a partnership that laid the foundation for **Econutri**. Read more [here](#).

Stand-Out Accomplishments

Impactful Publications

As **Econutri** enters its final six months (ending April 2026), the consortium highlights a series of recent peer-reviewed publications and partner contributions, in the year 2025 – underscoring the scientific progress and real-world relevance of the nutrient-smart innovations.

Published by ATB & ILVO

- [Acidification of animal slurry in housing and during storage to reduce NH3 and GHG emissions-recent advancements and future perspectives](#)
Wajid Umar, Chari Vandebussche, Elio Dinuccio, Dong Hongmin, Barbara Amon, Waste Management, Volume 203, 15 July 2025, 114856

Published by UNITO

- [Biodegradable Polymers for Plant Nutrient Delivery and Recovery](#)
Alice Boarino*, Nicola Carrara, Elio Padoan, Luisella Celi, and Harm-Anton Klok
Macromolecular Bioscience, Volume 25, Issue 8, August 14 2025, 2500042.
- [Strigolactones affect the stomatal and transcriptomic memory of repeated drought stress in tomato.](#)
Ivan Visentin, Eva Campo, Diana Davydenko, Paolo Korwin Krukowski, Giulia Russo, Claudio Lovisolo, Andrea Schubert, Francesca Cardinale
Plant Stress, 15(100740), 2025.

Published by AUA & UAL

- [Sodium accumulation management in a closed-loop soilless cropping system using ion selective electrodes and a novel Decision Support System](#)
Giannothanasis, E., Karavidas, I., Ntanasi, T. Ntatsi, G., Thompson, R.B., Savvas, D.
Smart Agricultural Technology 12, December 2025, 101366.

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Published by AUA

- [Exploring nutrient reduction strategies without yield losses in hydroponic lettuce production](#)
Evangelos Giannothanasias, Theodora Ntanasi, Ioannis Karavidas, George P. Spyrou, Damianos Neocleous, Georgia Ntatsi, Dimitrios Savvas, 2025.
- [Developing and validating a modelling approach linked with ion selective electrodes to control pollution of water resources from greenhouse crops](#)
Giannothanasias Evangelos, Cedeño Juan, Ntatsi Georgia, Thompson Rodney, Savvas Dimitrios, Journal of Environmental Management, Volume 387, July 2025, 125792.

Published by UTH

- [Cascade Hydroponics as a Means to Increase the Sustainability of Cropping Systems: Evaluation of Functional, Growth, and Fruit Quality Traits of Melons](#)
Zoe Karachaliou, Ioannis Naounoulis, Nikolaos Katsoulas, Efi Levizou, Sustainability 2025, 17(10), 4527.

Published by UTAD

- [Can nature-based biochar and biochar nanoparticles diminish the impacts of silver nanoparticles and microplastics on microbially-driven stream detrital ecosystem?](#)
Rupesh Kumar Singh, Arunava Pradhan, Virgílio Falco, Francisco Saraiva, Cláudia Pascoal, Henrique Trindade, Fernanda Cássio, João Ricardo Sousa, Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances, Volume 20, November 2025, 100903.

The growing list of peer-reviewed outputs across soil, greenhouse, manure, hydroponics, and ecosystem research demonstrates the strong scientific foundation of **Econutri's** innovations. These findings support advances in nutrient efficiency, pollution reduction, and more resilient, circular agri-food systems across Europe.

The full publication list is available on the website [here](#) and also on the [Zenodo](#) platform.

Policy Insights: Governing Nutrient Innovation for a Fair and Sustainable Agri-Food Future

To uncover the socioeconomic framework our partner ESSRG studies how different groups: both developers, innovators and consumers, perceive novel nutrient smart technologies. Watch the [video](#) and learn more about the first eDelphi Survey [here](#).

An upcoming survey will provide insights to help shape the policy debate on **Responsible Research and Innovation** in agri-food systems. The message for policymakers is clear: we need fair governance that ensures nutrient-smart innovations deliver real benefits for farmers and the environment.

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Work Package Highlights

WP1 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation (AUA, SPI)

WP1 reported strong progress across communication, dissemination, exploitation, clustering, and EU–China cooperation, with all milestones achieved and most KPIs already surpassed. Key updates included the development of the Final PDEC, increased digital outreach (website, LinkedIn, YouTube, WeChat), stakeholder engagement, and preparations for upcoming exploitation, clustering activities, and the first **Econutri** Hackathon.

WP2 – Innovative Technologies for Organic Matrices (UNITO, NIBIO, HAAS)

WP2 partners advanced technologies for nutrient recovery, compost optimisation, and manure/slurry application, reducing losses from organic waste streams. Pilot greenhouse and field models across Europe show strong potential to maintain yields while lowering nutrient pollution and supporting climate-smart agriculture.

WP3 – Innovative Cropping Technologies (WUR, UAL, UTH, NAU, CAU, Stanley)

WP3 made strong progress in developing smart fertilisation and precision-agriculture technologies that reduce nitrogen and phosphorus losses while improving nutrient-use efficiency. Field trials across Europe and China showed major reductions in nutrient leaching, water use, and emissions, while maintaining or increasing crop yields. DSS tools, drone-based applications, intercropping systems, and advanced soilless innovations are now delivering practical, climate-smart solutions for farmers.

WP4 – Nature-Based Technologies for GHG & NH₃ Reduction (EV ILVO, ATB, CAU)

WP4 is advancing nature-based and low-emission technologies across barns, manure storage, greenhouses, and fields, exceeding its KPI targets with 18 mitigation protocols and 18 pilot studies. Trials show major reductions in NH₃, CH₄, and N₂O emissions through biochar, improved manure management, feed strategies, and smart application techniques. Field results confirm that recovered nutrients and optimised organic fertilisers can maintain crop productivity while significantly lowering environmental impacts.

WP5 – Environmental Impacts & Socioeconomic Assessment (IGZ, ESSRG)

WP5 evaluates the environmental and socio-economic impacts of key **Econutri** innovations through modelling, Life Cycle Assessment, and

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stakeholder research. Early findings show substantial environmental benefits—such as reduced water use, fertiliser inputs, and emissions—while socio-economic studies highlight strong stakeholder motivation but also real-life difficulties in using these innovations.

WP6 – Data Management & system-level analysis (JHI, NIBIO)

WP6 advanced data harmonisation through the launch of the **Econutri** Access Database and introduced new modelling and evidence tools such as CropGOBLIN and a major NBS systematic review. Expert insights from the e-Delphi process highlight agroforestry, microbial composting and integrated farming as the most impactful solutions, guiding the final policy recommendations and deliverable D6.4 synthesis.

Econutri in the spotlight

Between June 2025 and October 2025, **Econutri** partners actively participated in conferences, educational events, and field visits across Europe and China – showcasing innovative, nature-based nutrient solutions and inspiring agronomists, scientists, and innovators on how to reduce waste and emissions.

Highlights are listed below.

22-27 June 2025 – 4 partners (**AUA, UAL, UTH, IGZ**) present **Econutri** research at [GreenSys2025](#), Almería, Spain

10 July 2025 – Educational Visit to UTH’s Pilot Greenhouse Park in Velestino, Greece.

21 July 2025 – **AUA** Welcomes Students from Jiangxi Agricultural University (China)

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14–18 July 2025 – **AUA** organizes a 5-day **Summer School**, bringing together students, researchers, and stakeholders for a week of learning, sharing, and innovation. As part of the programme, a series of [video interviews](#) with participants and stakeholders were carried out, capturing their experiences and insights. [Photos and videos](#) were collected throughout the week to document the activities and atmosphere.

9-16 August 2025 – **AUA** visits **China** for a series of scientific and networking activities with the project's Chinese partners. (from Beijing to Shouguang)

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27–28 August 2025 – **AUA** team member visits **Clean Grow, UK** to receive more specialised training on the use of the Ion specific electrodes tested and optimised in WP3.

12 September 2025 – **AUA** at the [Growing Media 2025](#) Symposium, **Germany**

16-19 September 2025 – SPI at [IASP2025](#) World Conference in Beijing, China showcasing Econutri and its scalable real world solutions. The presentation highlighted the project’s 24 innovative technologies, which are being validated and demonstrated in operational agricultural environments across Europe and China.

25 September 2025 – WUR

presents Econutri and the Virtual Lysimeter to Supply Companies, For improving the horticultural production systems.

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9 October 2025 – Celebrating 16 Years of Collaboration: From Warwick–CAU Partnership to the Econutri Horizon Europe Project.

A testament to how long-term collaboration can grow from a single research initiative into a global partnership shaping the future of sustainable agriculture.

10 October 2025 – Corn Field Visit of all partners to UTAD’s Demonstration Site in Barcelos (near Braga), Portugal

15 October 2025 – AUA welcomes HAAFS team and conducts field visit to stakeholder “MAGIKOS KIPOS”, Viotia, Greece

15-17 October 2025 – ATB and WUR at the [19th RAMIRAN Conference](#) in Wageningen, NL

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17 October 2025 – University of Thessaly (UTH) Showcases Innovative Cascade Hydroponics Research in Horti Daily EU Magazine

Looking into the University of Thessaly’s work on Cascade Hydroponics within the EcoNutri Project

As part of the EU-funded EcoNutri project, researchers from the Laboratory of Agricultural Constructions and Environmental Control at the University of Thessaly are pioneering a cutting-edge approach to sustainable agriculture through cascade hydroponic systems, a novel, nature-based method designed to minimize nutrient losses and environmental impact while maximizing resource efficiency.

Future Events

1. [Arable Scotland 2025](#) hosted by JHI, on February 24 2026
2. [UK Legume Research Community – 2026 Conference](#) hosted by JHI from 5–7 May 2026
3. [The International Legume Society – 2026 Conference](#), Dubrovnik, Croatia from 8 – 12 June 2026

4. WUR is organizing in Dec, Jan, Feb. and March, monthly update meetings with VL growers.
5. AUA is preparing the [Hackathon for Dec 15-16 2025](#).
6. WUR is preparing the Hackathon for January 2026 and a report to be published on the Na trails in cucumber and strawberry.
7. UNITO is organizing a trip to China to visit Chinese partners and stakeholders at the end of January 2026.
8. UNITO is organizing a school event on 11 February 2026.

Econutri Partners

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Project Coordinator

Dimitrios Savvas – [Agricultural University of Athens](#)
 email: dsavvas@aua.gr

